

Transparent Phase Change Materials for Scalable Latent-Heat Thermophotovoltaic Batteries

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Abstract

Latent-heat thermophotovoltaic (TPV) batteries are a promising approach for long-duration energy storage and dispatchable renewable power generation. Their scalability, however, is limited by the low thermal conductivity of most high-temperature phase change materials (PCMs), particularly during discharge when a solid crust forms and impedes heat transfer. This work presents an idealized theoretical analysis of a TPV battery architecture employing optically transparent PCMs, which enable both conductive and radiative heat transfer through the storage medium. A quasi-one-dimensional model is developed to simulate the thermal and electrical behavior of systems with opaque, fully transparent, and phase-dependent-transparency PCMs. Under the simplifying assumptions of perfect transparency and ideal blackbody radiation, results show that transparency markedly enhances emitter temperatures and power output, especially in the later stages of discharge, by alleviating the thermal bottlenecks associated with solidification. Moreover, transparent PCMs allow for the use of thicker storage layers without degrading performance, effectively decoupling system efficiency from storage capacity. While based on idealized assumptions, these findings establish an upper performance bound and underscore the transformative potential of radiatively transparent PCMs, motivating future experimental efforts to identify and characterize real high-temperature PCMs with partial or phase-dependent transparency under operational conditions.

Keywords: thermophotovoltaics, thermal energy storage, latent heat, phase change materials

1 Introduction

Thermophotovoltaic (TPV) batteries have recently gained attention as a promising solution for long-duration energy storage and dispatchable power generation from renewable energy sources [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7]. These systems can be charged using low-cost electricity

from the grid or from renewable sources such as wind and solar power [1], [2], or alternatively, by directly harvesting concentrated solar energy [4], [5], [6], [7]. The energy is stored in the form of ultra-high temperature heat—typically exceeding 1000 °C—and can be converted back into electricity on demand using TPV generators.

TPV devices function similarly to solar cells, but instead of harvesting sunlight, they convert thermal radiation into electricity via the photovoltaic effect [8], [9], [10], [11]. Their close-coupled geometry—with the TPV cell placed near a thermal emitter—enables the implementation of photon recycling strategies to significantly improve efficiency. In particular, out-of-band (sub-bandgap) photons, which are too low in energy to generate electron–hole pairs, can be reflected back to the emitter instead of being absorbed as waste heat.

The most successful photon recycling approach to date involves placing a high-reflectivity mirror behind the TPV cell. This mirror reflects the unused out-of-band radiation back to the emitter, where it can be reabsorbed, effectively recycling the energy [12], [13]. Thanks to the development of mirrors with average sub-bandgap reflectivities in the range of 97 to 99%, recent experiments have demonstrated TPV conversion efficiencies exceeding 40%—defined as the ratio of electrical output to the total heat absorbed by the cell [14], [15]. This level of efficiency is comparable to that of modern steam-based turbogenerators [16], with the added benefit that TPV performance is less sensitive to system size, making it well suited for both small- and large-scale applications.

TPV systems are particularly compatible with ultra-high temperature thermal storage, as thermal radiation becomes the dominant mode of heat transfer at elevated temperatures. This allows for direct conversion of stored radiative energy into electricity, enabling compact and efficient energy recovery.

Thermal energy storage systems for TPV applications have been proposed using both sensible heat and latent heat approaches. Sensible heat storage [17] can involve either liquid media (e.g., molten metals [2]) or solid media (e.g., graphite or other refractory ceramics [18]). These systems do not involve complex phase transitions, but they typically offer limited energy density, unless operated at extremely high temperatures, which are needed to achieve sufficient energy content and enable meaningful TPV power generation during discharge.

In contrast, latent heat storage systems using phase change materials (PCMs)—such as silicon or ferrosilicon alloys [1], [3], [6]—can achieve much higher energy densities due to the significant enthalpy change during melting and solidification. However, these systems involve more complex solid–liquid interactions, including interface dynamics and volume change effects, which add engineering challenges [19], [20], [21], [22], [23].

A common challenge for both sensible and latent heat systems is the significant drop in thermal conductivity of most materials at very high temperatures [24], [25], [26], [27]. Low thermal conductivity hinders efficient heat extraction, limiting the effective thickness or volume of the storage material that can be discharged efficiently [1], [3], [5], [6]. As a result, the total energy density of the system becomes constrained—not just by the intrinsic properties of the material, but also by the need to maintain efficient heat transfer pathways. This may force the use of additional volume for heat exchangers or limit the usable portion of the storage material, ultimately impacting system performance and scalability [1].

This issue is particularly pronounced in latent heat configurations, where a solid crust forms and grows opposite to the direction of heat flow during discharge [3]. Over time, this solidified layer acts as a thermal barrier, significantly impeding energy transfer from the remaining liquid PCM to the energy converter. As the solid crust thickens, it increases thermal resistance, reduces power output, and degrades overall system performance

In this work, I explore and analyze a potential solution to the scalability limitations of latent heat TPV batteries by introducing the use of transparent PCMs (TPCMs) for thermal energy storage, building upon the conceptual framework proposed in a 2020 patent [28]. The core idea is to replace conventional opaque PCMs with transparent or semi-transparent materials, allowing thermal radiation to propagate through the PCM volume, in addition to conduction. This dual-mode heat transfer mechanism can significantly reduce the temperature gradients that develop in the solid phase of opaque PCMs during discharge, particularly near the heat extraction surfaces. By alleviating these gradients, the approach aims to improve heat transfer, enhance power output, and enable the use of thicker PCM layers, ultimately supporting the design of more scalable and energy-dense TPV battery systems.

Because transparency depends on wavelength, temperature, crystallinity, and defect density—and because almost no experimental data exists for these materials under repeated melting–

solidification cycles—it is not yet possible to predict whether high transparency can be preserved under operating conditions. For this reason, the present work focuses on an idealized, upper-bound scenario in which the PCM is assumed to be perfectly transparent. This theoretical framework allows us to quantify the maximum achievable benefits of transparency—enhanced thermal transport, higher emitter temperatures, improved TPV conversion efficiency, and greater power density—thereby providing a benchmark for the concept’s potential and motivating future experimental research into practical high-temperature transparent PCMs for scalable, high-efficiency TPV-based thermal energy storage systems.

Section 2 presents a detailed description of the proposed TPV battery architecture and the quasi-one-dimensional analytical model used to evaluate its performance. This includes the geometric configuration of the system, the governing heat transfer equations for both conduction and volumetric radiation through the PCM, the modeling of the TPV converter using the detailed balance approach, and the boundary conditions and material parameters adopted for the simulations. Section 3 discusses the main results, comparing the thermal and electrical performance of systems employing opaque, fully transparent, and phase-dependent transparency PCMs. The analysis examines temperature profiles, emitter surface temperatures, power density evolution, integrated TPV efficiency, and the effect of PCM thickness and thermal conductivity on system behavior, highlighting how transparency mitigates the insulating effect of solid crust formation. Finally, Section 4 provides a brief outlook on potential high-temperature transparent PCM candidates, considering key selection criteria such as melting temperature, latent heat of fusion, high-temperature optical transparency, and the influence of crystallinity and microstructural quality on transmittance.

2 System description and methodology

Figure 1 illustrates several conceptual configurations for integrating transparent PCMs into latent heat thermal energy storage systems coupled with TPV generators, following the framework introduced in [28]. Two simplified scenarios are considered: (i) a PCM that is fully transparent (referred to as full-transparency PCM; panels a, c, e), and (ii) a PCM that is transparent in the solid phase but opaque in the liquid phase (phase-dependent-transparency PCM; panels b, d, f).

Panels (a) and (b) show the configurations investigated in this work, where the PCM is enclosed between two opaque surfaces: a front emitter facing the TPV cells, and a rear emitter adjacent to the heat insulation. In the case of full transparency PCM (panel a), during discharge, heat released by the solidifying PCM is conducted both inward (toward the front emitter) and outward (toward the rear emitter). Simultaneously, thermal radiation is exchanged between the rear and front emitters through the PCM volume. The front emitter combines both conductive and radiative contributions and re-emits the total energy flux toward the TPV cells. In the case of the phase-dependent-transparency PCM (panel b), the process is similar, except that thermal radiation is exchanged only between the solid–liquid interface and the front emitter through the solid PCM phase. Consequently, no outward heat flux occurs, and all the energy released at the liquid–solid interface is directed inward toward the front emitter.

Panels (c) and (d) introduce a more advanced concept, where the front emitter is removed, allowing direct radiative coupling between the rear emitter (in the full transparency case) or the liquid-solid interface (in the phase-dependent case) and the TPV cells. This configuration avoids the thermal resistance associated with heat conduction across the front emitter, potentially increasing the effective emitter temperature and improving system performance. However, special attention must be given to the phase state of the PCM, as the presence of a solid crust near the TPV cells is essential—it acts as a structural barrier, effectively containing the liquid PCM.

Finally, panels (e) and (f) illustrate a further advancement of the concept, inspired by the light-pipe TPV architecture [29], [30], [31], in which the transparent PCM acts as an optical waveguide, preserving direct radiative coupling between the rear emitter (for the full transparency scenario) or the liquid-solid interface (for the phase-dependent scenario) and the TPV cells. By channeling thermal radiation through the PCM without introducing refractive index mismatches, this configuration enhances radiative energy transfer and supports higher power density generation at the TPV receiver.

Figure 1. Conceptual configurations for integrating transparent phase-change materials (PCMs) into latent-heat thermophotovoltaic (TPV) batteries. Panels (a, c, e) correspond to the full-transparency scenario, while panels (b, d, f) represent the phase-dependent-transparency scenario. (a, b) Configurations investigated in this work, where the PCM is enclosed between two opaque surfaces: a front emitter facing the TPV cells and a rear emitter adjacent to the thermal insulation. Heat released at the solid–liquid interface is transferred by conduction and radiation, with the front emitter re-emitting the total flux toward the TPV cells. (c, d) Modified concept in which the front emitter is removed, enabling direct radiative coupling between the rear emitter (full-transparency case) or the solid–liquid interface (phase-dependent case) and the TPV cells, thereby eliminating conduction-related losses across the front emitter. A solid crust adjacent to the TPV cells is required to contain the liquid PCM. (e, f) Advanced concept inspired by light-pipe TPV architectures, where the transparent PCM functions as an optical waveguide. Radiation from the rear emitter (full-transparency case) or the solid–liquid interface (phase-dependent case) is channeled directly to the TPV cells through the PCM, minimizing optical losses and enabling high power-density generation

This study focuses on the configurations shown in panels (a) and (b), modeled using a cylindrical geometry, similar to the one presented in [3] (**Figure 2**). The system dynamics are described by a quasi-one-dimensional analytical model, adapted from the approach in [3], to capture transient behavior during charge and discharge. This model assumes a quasi-stationary regime in which the solid-liquid interface is represented by a moving cylindrical boundary located at a radial distance $r_m(t)$ from the axial center of the system (**Figure 2**). The analysis is conducted under the assumption of an adiabatic (i.e., lossless) thermal insulation, and natural convection in the liquid phase is neglected. Consequently, the one-dimensional Fourier conduction law is valid for modeling heat transfer in both the solid and liquid phases:

$$Q_{l,s} = 2\pi r L k_{l,s} \frac{dT}{dr} \quad (1)$$

Integrating Equation (1) in the solid and liquid domains yields expressions for the boundary temperatures T_1 (at $r = R_1$) and T_2 (at $r = R_2$) as functions of the melting temperature (T_m):

$$T_1 = T_m - \frac{Q_s}{2\pi L k_s} \ln \left| \frac{r_m(t)}{R_1} \right| \quad (2)$$

$$T_2 = T_m + \frac{Q_l}{2\pi L k_l} \ln \left| \frac{R_2}{r_m(t)} \right| \quad (3)$$

Here, k_s and k_l denote the thermal conductivities of the solid and liquid phases, respectively.

In addition to conductive heat transfer, the transparency of the PCM allows for radiative heat transfer between the rear emitter surface at $r = R_2$ (full transparency scenario) or the solid-liquid interface at $r = r_m$ (phase-dependent scenario) and the front emitter internal surface at $r = R_1$. Under the assumptions of ideal blackbody behavior, full transparency of the PCM (i.e., 100% transmittance), and infinitely long, concentric cylindrical surfaces, the net radiative heat flux through the PCM is given by:

$$Q_r = 2\pi R_1 L \sigma (T_x^4 - T_1^4) \quad (4)$$

where σ the Stefan Boltzmann constant and $T_x = T_2$ in the full-transparency scenario or $T_x = T_m$ in the phase-dependent scenario.

The total heat transferred through the front emitter (to the front surface at $r = R_e$) is the sum of conductive and radiative components. Using the integrated form of Fourier's law, the emitter front surface temperature T_e is given by:

$$T_e = T_1 - \frac{Q_s + Q_r}{2\pi L k_e} \ln \left| \frac{R_1}{R_e} \right| \quad (5)$$

where k_e is the thermal conductivity of the front emitter. The radiative exchange between the external surface of the front emitter (at $r=R_e$) and the TPV converter is modeled using the detailed balance method described in [32], resulting in:

$$(Q_s + Q_r)/\pi = -\dot{E}(0, \infty, T_e, qV) + \dot{E}(\varepsilon_G, \infty, T_c, qV) + \frac{\rho_{BR}}{1-\rho_{BR}} \dot{E}(0, \infty, T_e, qV) \quad (6)$$

where the radiative energy flux in vacuum, in the normal direction, and per unit solid angle, \dot{E} , is defined as:

$$\dot{E}(\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, T, \mu) = \frac{2}{h^3 c^2} \int_{\varepsilon_1}^{\varepsilon_2} \frac{\varepsilon^3 d\varepsilon}{\exp[(\varepsilon - \mu)/kT] - 1} \quad (7)$$

In this expression, T is the surface temperature, $\mu = qV$ is the chemical potential (with V being the TPV cell voltage), and the integration is carried out over photon energies from ε_1 to ε_2 . Equation (6) assumes sharp cut-off absorptivity at the bandgap energy ε_G , a unity view factor between the emitter and the cells, and the presence of a back reflector with reflectivity ρ_{BR} .

Given the adiabatic condition, the net energy transferred from the liquid to the solid must match the energy required to melt the PCM in the annular region between $r_m(t)$ and $r_m(t + \Delta t)$:

$$(Q_l - Q_s)\Delta t = 2\pi L L_f \rho_l r_m(t) (r_m(t + \Delta t) - r_m(t)) \quad (8)$$

where L_f and ρ_l are the latent heat of fusion and the liquid PCM density, respectively. This expression applies directly to the full-transparency scenario. In the phase-dependent-transparency case, the energy balance is modified by subtracting the radiative contribution Q_r , since a fraction of the thermal energy is directly emitted from the opaque liquid–solid interface toward the front emitter. The corresponding substitution is therefore $(Q_l - Q_s) \rightarrow (Q_l - Q_s - Q_r)$ in Equation (8).

Since the container is adiabatic, all energy extracted from the PCM is radiated through the emitter, leading to the following energy balance:

$$E_{tot}(t + \Delta t) = E_{tot}(t) - (Q_s + Q_r)\Delta t \quad (9)$$

The total stored energy, E_{tot} , which includes both sensible and latent heat, is given by:

$$E_{tot}/(2\pi L) = \rho_s c_{ps} \int_{R_1}^{r_m} r T_s(r) dr + \rho_l c_{pl} \int_{r_m}^{R_2} r T_l(r) dr + \rho_l L_f (R_2^2 - r_m^2)/2 \quad (10)$$

which neglects the energy stored in the emitters. The integrals in Equation (10) can be evaluated analytically using the temperature profiles derived from Equation (1). These yield:

$$\int_{R_1}^{r_m} r T_s(r) dr = \frac{1}{2} \left[r_m^2 T_m - R_1^2 T_1 - \frac{Q_s}{4\pi L k_s} (r_m^2 - R_1^2) \right] \quad (11)$$

$$\int_{r_m}^{R_2} r T_l(r) dr = \frac{1}{2} \left[R_2^2 T_2 - r_m^2 T_m - \frac{Q_l}{2\pi L k_l} (r_m^2 - R_2^2) \cdot (2 \ln|r_m| - 0.5) \right] \quad (12)$$

The coupled equations (2) through (6) and (8) through (9) can be solved numerically to obtain the unknowns T_1 , T_2 , T_e , Q_l , Q_s , Q_r and $r_m(t+\Delta t)$.

The electrical power output from the TPV converter is computed as described in [32]:

$$P_{el} = \pi A_c qV \times \left\{ \dot{N}(\varepsilon_G, \infty, T_e, 0) - \left[1 + 2n_s^2 \left(\frac{1-\rho_{BR}}{2} - \frac{1-\eta_{int}}{\eta_{int}} \right) \dot{N}(\varepsilon_G, \infty, T_c, qV) \right] \right\} \quad (13)$$

with \dot{N} representing the spectral photon flux:

$$\dot{N}(\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, T, \mu) = \frac{2}{h^3 c^2} \int_{\varepsilon_1}^{\varepsilon_2} \frac{\varepsilon^2 d\varepsilon}{\exp[(\varepsilon-\mu)/kT]-1} \quad (14)$$

As with the energy flux expression, \dot{N} quantifies the number of photons emitted per unit solid angle and energy interval. Here, n_s is the refractive index of the semiconductor and η_{int} is the internal luminescent efficiency - i.e., the proportion of electron-hole pairs that recombine radiatively within the cell.

The instantaneous system conversion efficiency is defined as the ratio between the electrical power output P_{el} , given by Equation (13), and the net radiative power absorbed by the TPV cell. Under the assumption of a unity view factor between the emitter and the cell, this absorbed power corresponds to the sum of the conductive and radiative heat fluxes, $Q_s + Q_r$, as defined in Equation (6):

$$\eta_{TPV} = \frac{P_{el}}{Q_s + Q_r} \quad (15)$$

Finally, the integrated TPV efficiency and the average power density are defined, respectively, as the ratio of the total electrical energy generated to the total thermal energy absorbed during the entire discharge, and the ratio of the total electrical energy to the product of discharge duration and TPV cell area. These time-averaged performance metrics, as opposed to their instantaneous counterparts given in Equations (13) and (15), provide a more representative assessment of the system's overall performance. As such, they will be also used to evaluate and compare the effectiveness of different system configurations.

Figure 2. (a) Schematic representation of the cylindrical thermal storage system with transparent phase change material (PCM). The system is composed of concentric cylindrical regions: the thermal emitter (at radius R_e), the internal crucible wall (between R_e and R_1), the solid PCM (between R_1 and the time-dependent solid-liquid interface $r_m(t)$), and the liquid PCM (between $r_m(t)$ and the outer boundary at R_2). Due to the optical transparency of the PCM, radiative heat transfer Q_r occurs directly through the PCM from the outer surface (at $R=R_2$) to the inner wall (at $R=R_1$), in addition to conduction (Q_s and Q_l) in the solid and liquid regions, respectively. Temperature boundaries T_e , T_1 , T_2 , and the melting temperature T_m are indicated. (b) Radial cross-section of the same system, highlighting the cylindrical symmetry and spatial distribution of each region. This view emphasizes the radial variation of temperature, as well as the location of the moving solid-liquid interface $r_m(t)$.

3 Results and discussion

This section presents simulation results for a cylindrical latent heat TPV battery, as described in the previous section, considering three scenarios: (i) an opaque PCM, (ii) a fully transparent PCM, and (iii) a phase-dependent transparency PCM. For the opaque case, we start modeling pure silicon, which has been widely investigated in previous studies as a high-temperature PCM (e.g., [1], [3], [5], [6], [7]). For the transparent cases, we first consider a hypothetical material with the same thermophysical properties as silicon but with ideal optical transparency: either fully transparent in both phases or transparent in the solid phase and opaque in the liquid phase. We then investigate the effect of varying the thermal conductivity of the PCM to evaluate its influence on system performance. Assuming 100% transmittance in the relevant phase(s) not only simplifies the model but also provides an upper bound on the performance potential of the concept. Although no known material currently satisfies these idealized properties, such an

approach is appropriate for a first theoretical exploration, as it isolates the role of transparency while holding other variables constant, thereby clarifying its impact on the thermal and electrical performance of the system.

All simulations are performed using the system parameters listed in **Table 1**, unless otherwise specified.

Table 1. List of parameters used for simulations

Parameter	Variable	Value
TPV cell bandgap	ε_G	0.75 eV
TPV cell refractive index	n_s	3.5
TPV cell temperature	T_c	27°C
Back surface reflectivity	ρ_{BR}	0.90
Internal photoluminescent efficiency	η_{int}	0.84
PCM density (solid and liquid)	$\rho_s = \rho_l$	2330 kg/m ³
PCM latent heat	L_f	1165 kWh/m ³
PCM melting point	T_m	1414 °C
Solid PCM thermal conductivity	k_s	29 W/m-K
Liquid PCM thermal conductivity	k_l	60 W/m-K
Front emitter thermal conductivity	k_e	40 W/m-K
Front emitter external surface radius	R_e	5 cm
Front emitter internal surface radius (PCM boundary)	R_1	7 cm
Rear emitter radius (PCM boundary)	R_2	20 cm

3.1 Dynamics of the system's discharge

Figure 3 presents the temporal evolution of the thermal and electrical performance of the system for both opaque and transparent PCMs. **Panels (a), (b) and (c)** display the radial temperature profiles across the system for the opaque (a), transparent (b) and phase-dependent transparency (c) PCMs, respectively, spanning from the front emitter surface at $r = R_e$ to the rear emitter at $r = R_2$. **Panel (d)** illustrates the evolution of the generated electrical power density

during discharge: solid lines correspond to phase-dependent-transparency PCMs, dot-dashed lines to fully transparent PCMs, and dashed lines to opaque PCMs.

The comparison reveals that optical transparency in the PCM significantly increases the temperature of the front emitter surface (T_e at $r = R_e$), thereby enhancing the electrical power output. This effect becomes increasingly pronounced during the later stages of discharge, where the opaque PCM forms a solid crust with low thermal conductivity, which inhibits efficient heat transfer from the remaining liquid core. In contrast, transparent PCMs enable direct radiative transfer—either from the hotter rear emitter (fully transparent case) or from the melting front (phase-dependent case)—to the front emitter at $r = R_1$. This mechanism alleviates the insulating effect of the solid crust, thereby sustaining a higher front-emitter temperature and maintaining elevated power output throughout the discharge.

An important observation concerns the evolution of the PCM temperature profiles during discharge. For the opaque and phase-dependent-transparency PCM cases (panels a and c), the liquid region remains nearly isothermal, with most of the temperature drop occurring across the solid layer. The absence of a temperature gradient in the liquid is a consequence of the adiabatic condition at the rear emitter: all heat released at the solid–liquid interface is conducted inward toward the front emitter, generating a gradient only within the solid phase. In contrast, for the fully transparent PCM, the temperature profile evolves differently. At the beginning of the discharge, the liquid PCM also exhibits a nearly uniform temperature, similar to the opaque and phase-dependent transparency cases. However, as the discharge progresses, the thermal behavior changes rapidly, and the maximum temperature shifts to the solid–liquid interface. This transition leads to bidirectional heat conduction: heat flows both inward toward the front emitter and outward toward the rear emitter. As a result, both boundary surfaces (at $r = R_1$ and $r = R_2$) receive heat from the melting front via conduction. The rear emitter at $r = R_2$, which is assumed to behave as a blackbody, then re-radiates energy inward through the transparent PCM, which helps sustain a high temperature at the front emitter external surface (at $r = R_e$).

In summary, a fully transparent PCM establishes two parallel thermal pathways—inward and outward—from the melting front to the radiating surfaces, thereby reducing the effective conduction distance required before heat is transferred radiatively. This dual conduction–radiation mechanism enhances the system’s ability to sustain high emitter temperatures,

particularly as the solid layer thickens during discharge. By contrast, a phase-dependent-transparency PCM, with an opaque liquid phase and a transparent solid phase, enables direct radiative transfer of latent heat from the solid–liquid interface to the front emitter. In this configuration, energy transfer relies predominantly on radiation rather than conduction, resulting in the highest front-emitter temperatures and power output throughout discharge.

Figure 3. (a) Temporal evolution of the thermal and electrical performance of the TPV battery for opaque and transparent PCMs. Panels (a–c) show the radial temperature profiles for the opaque, fully transparent, and phase-dependent-transparency cases, respectively. Panel (d) presents the corresponding evolution of electrical power density, with solid lines representing the phase-dependent-transparency PCM, dot-dashed lines the fully transparent PCM, and dashed lines the opaque PCM.

3.2 Enhancement of Storage Capacity via PCM Transparency

The improved energy transfer between the melting front and the TPV generator in the cases of fully transparent and phase-dependent transparency PCM opens the possibility of using larger PCM volumes without compromising system performance. For opaque materials, the maximum

usable PCM thickness—defined here by the gap $R_2 - R_1$ —is limited due to the formation of a low-conductivity solid crust during discharge. This crust progressively hinders heat conduction from the liquid phase to the emitter, reducing output power over time. In contrast, a transparent PCM enables more efficient heat transfer through radiation, even as solidification progresses. As a result, thicker PCM layers can be used without sacrificing output power, effectively enabling higher energy and power capacities.

This effect is illustrated in **Figure 4**, where panels (a) and (c) shows the integrated TPV efficiency, defined as the ratio of the total electrical energy generated to the total thermal energy absorbed by the TPV cells during the entire discharge as a function of the PCM thickness (panel a) and total discharge duration (panel c). Panels (b) and (d) present the averaged power density, calculated as the ratio of the total electrical energy to the product of discharge duration and TPV cell area, also as a function of the PCM thickness (panel b) and total discharge duration (panel d). Results are shown for opaque PCMs (dashed lines), fully transparent PCMs (dot-dashed lines), and phase-dependent-transparency PCMs (solid lines), each evaluated for three values of solid-phase thermal conductivity: 1, 10, and 30 W/m·K.

The results confirm that the presence of radiative heat-transfer pathways in transparent PCMs makes system performance far less sensitive to both PCM thickness and the solid-phase thermal conductivity. Even when the solid has low conductivity and the PCM layer is relatively thick, radiation from the rear emitter (fully transparent case) or from the solid–liquid interface (phase-dependent case) effectively delivers energy to the front emitter, mitigating the insulating effect of the solid crust. In contrast, opaque PCMs rely exclusively on conduction. As discharge proceeds, heat extraction from the liquid phase slows dramatically, prolonging discharge time (**Figure 4c, d**) and reducing both efficiency and power density. This reflects a fundamental trade-off in opaque systems: increasing storage capacity by thickening the PCM inevitably compromises performance due to restricted heat transfer through the solid.

Transparent PCMs overcome this trade-off. By sustaining radiative transport, they allow thicker PCM layers and longer discharge durations—hence greater storage capacity—without sacrificing emitter temperature, power output, or efficiency, even when the solid phase has low thermal conductivity. This makes overall system behavior largely independent of solid-phase conduction pathways. Such robustness is particularly valuable since PCM conductivity often

degrades during operation or processing due to grain boundaries, structural defects, or impurities. For example, the thermal conductivity of single-crystal silicon is an order of magnitude higher than that of amorphous silicon at room temperature [33]. Transparent PCMs, by enabling radiative energy transport, can maintain efficient performance even when conduction pathways are compromised.

Figure 4. Integrated TPV efficiency and average power density for opaque (dashed), fully transparent (dot-dashed), and phase-dependent-transparency (solid) PCMs, evaluated at three solid-phase thermal conductivities: 1 W/m·K (blue), 10 W/m·K (orange), and 30 W/m·K (green). Panels (a) and (c) show integrated efficiency as a function of PCM thickness and discharge duration, respectively, while panels (b) and (d) present the corresponding average power density.

It is important to note that the preceding results were obtained assuming a relatively high liquid-phase thermal conductivity (60 W/m·K) and neglecting convection in the liquid. This assumption is appropriate for the opaque and phase-dependent-transparency cases, where the liquid remains isothermal and all heat released at the solid–liquid interface is conducted inward through the solid phase. Consequently, the results for these two cases are independent of the

liquid-phase thermal conductivity. In the fully transparent case, however, temperature gradients within the liquid may give rise to buoyancy-driven convection, which would further enhance heat transfer. Since convective effects invariably improve liquid-phase heat transport, the results reported here for the fully transparent case should be regarded as a conservative estimate, representing the worst-case scenario under the assumptions of this study.

4 Material Considerations for High-Temperature TPCMs

In the preceding sections, we have seen that transparent PCMs can significantly enhance TPV battery performance, enabling increased energy capacity without compromising power density or conversion efficiency. The next critical challenge lies in identifying and developing suitable materials to enable the fabrication of experimental prototypes.

Transparent PCMs have been studied before, but only at low melting points (20–40 °C) for building applications [34], [35], where they were proposed as transparent thermal envelopes capable of absorbing solar heat during the day and releasing it at night. To date, however, there has been no investigation of transparent PCMs operating in the extreme temperature range required for TPV batteries—i.e., melting points near or above 1000 °C. Materials suited for such conditions must meet three demanding criteria: (i) a high melting temperature, (ii) a large enthalpy of fusion, and (iii) the ability to remain transparent or at least semi-transparent when heated to operational temperatures.

Among the many PCMs reported in the literature [36], fluoride salts emerge as particularly promising. Several members of this family combine high melting points, substantial heats of fusion, and documented transparency well above room temperature [36], [37], [38], [39]. Notable examples include MgF_2 (m.p. 1263 °C, $L_f = 938$ J/g, $k_{s,300\text{K}} = 3.15$ W/m-K) [40], [41], [42], LiF_2 (m.p. 849 °C, $L_f = 1041$ J/g, $k_{s,300\text{K}} = 4.01$ W/m-K) [37], CaF_2 (m.p. 1418 °C, $L_f = 381$ J/g, $k_{s,300\text{K}} = 9.17$ W/m-K) [37], [41], [42], and BaF_2 (m.p. 1368 °C, $L_f = 105$ J/g, $k_{s,300\text{K}} = 7.1$ W/m-K) [37], [41], [42]. In all cases, the thermal conductivity is expected to reach near or below 1 W/m-K at high temperatures, both in solid [43] and molten [44] state. At room temperature, single-crystal fluorides transmit efficiently from the visible well into the near- and mid-infrared, with the multiphonon absorption edge—defined here at $\alpha \approx 100$ m^{-1} —lying between ~ 6 μm and ~ 11 μm depending on the cation [37]. However, as the temperature rises

toward the melting point, this edge shifts toward shorter wavelengths; for instance, in LiF it moves from 6.3 μm at 27 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 4.9 μm in the molten state at 890 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ [37].

Beyond fluorides, several oxides also merit consideration as extreme-temperature transparent PCMs. These include Al_2O_3 (m.p. 2072 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, $L_f=1138$ J/g, $k_{s,300\text{K}}=30$ W/m-K, $k_{s,1300\text{K}}=8$ W/m-K [45]) and MgO (m.p. 2852 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, $L_f=1700$ J/g, $k_{s,400\text{K}}=30$ W/m-K, $k_{s,1300\text{K}}=8$ W/m-K [46]), both of which are highly transparent from the visible into the near-infrared in their crystalline form at room temperature. However, transparency also degrades at high temperature. For example, in single-crystal Al_2O_3 , the absorption coefficient at 4 μm increases from ~ 0.04 cm^{-1} at 300 K to ~ 1 cm^{-1} at 2000 K [47]. In the molten state, absorption coefficient at 4 μm ranges from ~ 20 cm^{-1} (at 2327 K) to ~ 1000 cm^{-1} at 3000 K, with even higher values at longer wavelengths [48]. These values correspond to 50 % attenuation lengths decreasing from ~ 0.35 mm ($\alpha \approx 20$ cm^{-1}) to ~ 6.9 μm ($\alpha \approx 1000$ cm^{-1}), showing that the melt becomes effectively opaque at these extreme temperatures. Although this loss of transparency in the liquid state limits the suitability of alumina for fully transparent PCM concepts, it could be advantageous in system variants where only the solid phase is transparent—such as the phase-dependent transparency configuration.

The difficulty of identifying a suitable transparent PCM is further compounded by the strong influence of crystallinity and microstructure on optical properties [38], [49]. Polycrystalline cubic materials—such as CaF_2 —can be processed to retain much of the single-crystal optical window if grain sizes are kept smaller than the characteristic wavelength of the transmitted radiation. In contrast, birefringent materials such as sapphire (Al_2O_3) and MgF_2 inherently suffer from grain-boundary scattering due to refractive index mismatch, often limiting them to a translucent state. High transmittance also requires a dense, defect-free microstructure without pores, secondary phases, or impurities [38], [49].

Even if a perfectly transparent PCM cannot be identified, partial transparency—whether in the solid phase, the liquid phase, or both—could still provide meaningful improvements. Any degree of radiative heat transfer through the PCM would alleviate the thermal bottlenecks associated with solid crust formation, moving system performance in the direction of the idealized results presented in this study. Such materials could therefore enable a substantial fraction of the efficiency and power density gains predicted here, making the pursuit of partially

transparent high-temperature PCMs a promising and practical step toward improved TPV battery performance.

5 Conclusions

This work has presented and analyzed the concept of using optically transparent phase change materials (TPCMs) to enhance the performance and scalability of latent-heat thermophotovoltaic (TPV) batteries. Two transparency scenarios were considered: a fully transparent PCM and a phase-dependent-transparency PCM, where the solid phase is transparent but the liquid phase is opaque.

Both cases alleviate the thermal bottlenecks typically associated with solidification in opaque systems, where a low-conductivity crust impedes heat transfer from the liquid core. Fully transparent PCMs achieve this by enabling dual-mode heat transport—conduction and volumetric radiation—between the melting front and the radiating surfaces. Phase-dependent-transparency PCMs, in contrast, provide a direct radiative channel from the solid–liquid interface to the front emitter, bypassing the need for conduction through the solid crust. In both cases, the result is higher emitter temperatures, sustained power output over longer discharge times, and the possibility of employing thicker PCM layers—directly addressing scalability challenges in latent-heat thermal storage.

Although the analysis was based on idealized assumptions of perfect transparency, the results establish an upper bound on performance, highlighting the transformative role of optical transparency in PCMs. Even partial transparency is expected to provide substantial benefits, particularly in systems where solid-phase thermal conductivity is limited by material degradation, grain boundaries, or impurities. In effect, transparent and phase-dependent-transparent PCMs break the conventional trade-off between energy capacity and output power that constrains current TPV battery designs.

Several candidate materials—including magnesium fluoride, lithium fluoride, calcium fluoride, and alumina—exhibit partial infrared transparency at high temperatures and may provide a foundation for practical transparent PCMs. Future work should focus on modeling systems with realistic, temperature- and wavelength-dependent optical properties, as well as experimental characterization of transmittance and emissivity at high temperatures and after repeated

melting–solidification cycles. Such efforts are essential for quantifying the practical benefits of transparency and guiding material development toward deployable TPV storage systems.

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Declaration of Interests

The author declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Alejandro Datas reports a relationship with Thermophoton that includes equity or stocks. Alejandro Datas has patent #ES2743794A1 issued to Universidad Politécnica de Madrid.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author used ChatGPT in order to improve the English grammar of this manuscript. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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